

KEY INDICATORS

With 2,876,052 hectares under organic management, France ranked first in terms of area under organic management, and 17% of the EU's organic farmland was in France. With 10% of its farmland being organic, France was slightly below the EU average of 10.6%. Growth from 2001 to 2022 was at almost 600%, thus higher than in the European Union. Regarding organic retail sales, with 12,076 million euros, France held rank two in the EU in 2022. With 6.1%, it had an above-EU-average organic share of the total food market.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

419,750 ha (1.5%)

2,876,052 ha (10%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

585%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

94,045 ha (0.6%)

1,589,609 ha (8.8%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

21,903 ha (2.1%)

224,024 ha (21.2%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

275,105 ha (2.7%)

962,038 ha (10%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

8,955 † (4.7%) (2020)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

10,364 (1.7%)

60,522 (15.2%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

60 (2017)

Processors

5,400

20,365

Importers

N/D

659

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

1,150 M €

12,076 M€ (6.1%)

Per Capita Consumption

18.9 €

176 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

950 %

Imports

N/D

277,414 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN FRANCE

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, based on AgenceBio, Eurostat and Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN FRANCE

Source: Agence Bio, Observatoire Bio

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

In the previous period, France halted maintenance payments, which contributed to the low share of certified organic land supported. In mainland France, support for maintenance was reintroduced as part of the national eco-scheme. This support was extended to land in conversion, in addition to the P2 conversion payments. The contrasting approaches to conversion and maintenance support lead to some very large differences in payments for some land uses. Although the expenditure per hectare is planned to remain relatively constant, the increased area supported is expected to lead to more than 3 times the annual expenditure compared with the previous period. Some regional governments and water agencies provide top-up support that is not included here.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	1,040 kha	3,384 kha (+225%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	3.6%	11.7% (+225%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	51%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	180 M€	603 ¹ M€ (+235%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	173 €	178 € (+3%)

¹Planned expenditure values for FR eco-schemes have been estimated from per hectare rates and R29 indicators

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027

ORGANIC SHARE

Organic Farming Support (P1/P2)	2,725 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	8,558 M€	24.2%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	2,718 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	49,742 M€	5.5%

Organic eco-scheme expenditure estimated from per hectare rates and R29 indicators. Regional top-up funding not included ^{*}including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	130	300	450	900	350
	2023	P2+P1	130 / +110	350 / +110	450 / +110	900 / +110	350 / +110
Change from 2019 to 2023			0%	+17%	0%	0%	0%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	0	0	0	0	0
	2023	P1/P2	110	110	110	110	110
Change from 2019 to 2023			∞	∞	∞	∞	∞
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		∞	∞	∞	∞	∞
	2023	P2+P1	+118%	+318%	+409%	+818%	+318%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing. P2 used for maintenance in Corsica and overseas territories. P2 maintenance in mainland France stopped from 2018. P1 eco-scheme also applies to land in conversion. Regional and water agency top-up funding not included.

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

France has had three national organic action plans since the first one was published in 2011. The latest one was in preparation but not published at the time the analysis was undertaken. In the previous plan, particular emphasis was placed on training, research and market information actions.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2018-22	15% of UAA by 2022	20% of public procurement by 2022
Current Action Plan	2024-30	Not yet available (18% of UAA by 2027 in CSP)	Not yet available

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN

(2015 - 2022)

Increase support and awareness of different funding sources; support for group conversion, access to land, and for producers affected by external contamination; support organic development in overseas territories

Identify priorities for balanced sector development, consistent with other strategies; organise liaison meetings with relevant actors; develop tools to facilitate supply contracts to deliver 20% public procurement goal, incl. Best practice guidelines; increase organic in hospitality catering, including staff training; promote exports; clarify conditions for using the AB logo and relationship to organic and environmental certification; adaptation of regulations esp. relating to plant and animal health

Encourage consumption with promotion campaign led by Agence Bio; communicate characteristics and benefits of organic products; consolidate and facilitate access to technical, economic, ecological and social information for producers; integrate organic in sustainable production courses; multiple training initiatives; strengthen organic research, including in the INRA Metaprogramme, define new mandate for Organic Research Council; development of statistical information system by Agence Bio; complete process of geolocating organic land parcels to facilitate data exchange; regional market observatories

CURRENT ACTION PLAN

(2024 - 2030)

PRODUCTION

Not yet available

MARKETS

Not yet available

INFORMATION

Not yet available

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in France is almost 5%. Organic aquaculture has been supported as part of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture, including investment aids, conversion support, promotion and research. Aquaculture was not highlighted in the previous national organic action plan. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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